

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF PORTABLE CAR AIR CONDITIONING TRAINER INTEGRATED WITH A CHARGING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Developing effective instructional tools is vital to improving hands-on learning experiences in technical-vocational education. However, there is a lack of portable and integrated trainers that simulate both air conditioning and charging systems in the automotive context. This study aimed to develop and evaluate a Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer integrated with a charging system as a teaching aid for students pursuing a Bachelor's in Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (BTVTEd) major in Automotive Technology. Employing a developmental and descriptive-evaluative research design, the trainer was constructed using locally available materials and aligned with curriculum standards. A total of 60 respondents, who comprised students, instructors, and industry technicians, evaluated the trainer based on design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability using a validated questionnaire. Results showed that the trainer performed within standard cooling temperatures (21°C–27°C), pressure ranges, and voltage outputs. It received an “Excellent” rating in all evaluated aspects, with mean scores ranging from 4.90 to 4.92. Significant differences in acceptability were found among the three respondent groups, particularly from technicians who provided more critical ratings. Nonetheless, the trainer was found highly acceptable across all groups. The findings affirm the trainer’s instructional value and highlight its potential for curriculum integration. Recommendations include incorporating industry feedback, enhancing features, conducting pilot tests, and patenting the trainer to promote further educational application and industry relevance.

Keywords: *Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer, Technical-Vocational Education, Instructional Tool Development, Automotive Technology, Trainer Evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Education is not solely about imparting knowledge; it must also equip students with the practical skills necessary for real-world applications. Training institutions play a crucial role in providing students with significant knowledge and skills as well as hands-on experiences. This, after all, is the pedagogical approach known as the “hands-on” approach, providing ample chances for the learners to execute and implement what they learn from school, making them more competent, resourceful, and self-reliant entrepreneurs.

By integrating real-world experiences in education, students gain academic knowledge alongside critical life skills, supporting a holistic educational approach that enables them to succeed in an ever-evolving environment (Yaodum et al., 2023). This, in turn, will equip the individual for future community engagements and satisfy one of the highest levels of learning—application, as outlined in Experiential Learning Theory. With this, the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA) formulates manpower and skills plans, sets appropriate skills standards and tests, coordinates and monitors manpower policies and programs, and provides policy directions and guidelines for resource allocation for the TVET institutions in both the private and public sectors ensuring students receive relevant and competency-based training parallel with industry demands.

Aligned with these efforts, UNESCO Education 2030 under the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4: Quality Education, emphasizes the importance of inclusive, accessible, and lifelong learning opportunities for all. Specifically, SDG 4.3 and 4.4 focus on expanding access to technical and vocational education, increasing the number of youths and adults equipped with technical and vocational skills ready for employment or entrepreneurship.

In response to these national and global educational priorities, Nueva Vizcaya State University (NVSU) offers automotive technology as one of the majors in the Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (BTVTED) program. This course offers subject specialization specifically, AT6 – (Automotive Technology 6) Unit Competency–Automotive Air Conditioning System Servicing, Repair and Maintenance, embedded under the CHED MEMORANDUM ORDER (CMO) No. 79 Series of 2017.

The course covers the service, repair, and maintenance of the automotive air-conditioning system. It includes topics on diagnosing and general check-ups, repair, and replacement of air-conditioning system components. The course further discusses automotive air-conditioning components and their operating principle. It also contains recovery, evacuating, retrofitting, recharging, and carry-out A/C performance test. Automotive specialization in NVSU prepares students to work in the automotive industry,

a sector that necessitates access to extensive hands-on instruction and proper training equipment.

However, the lack of facilities and equipment poses a significant challenge in delivering accessible and inclusive quality education. Asian Development Bank (2022) recognizes the funding limitations as a major obstacle in updating tools and equipment, noting that TESDA requires institutions to maintain appropriate and updated equipment and facilities for training on emerging technologies. Instructors are encouraged to develop trainers to enhance teaching and learning (Samonte and Torres, 2013). Kilag et al. (2023) stress the importance of addressing the issues in Technical-Vocational Education, including the promotion of innovative pedagogical approaches and investing in infrastructure and technology, while Castillo (2019) highlighted that teachers should use instructional technologies that are less expensive, ready-to-use, and beneficial for student learning. Moreover, Article XIV, Section 10 of the Philippine Constitution, which prioritizes research and development, invention, innovation, and their application, as well as science and technology education, training, and services.

The above-cited writing affirms the need for every training school to develop trainers to facilitate the effective and efficient delivery of technical instructions. Mock-ups are instructional innovations that serve as a developing tool that can be used to enhance students' performances. Thus, educational research and development (R&D) increases the potential impact of translating research results into usable products that will help improve educational outcomes.

A pre-survey conducted by the researcher revealed that four (4) out of five (5) institutions have no car air-conditioning trainer available, relying instead on actual car engines for laboratory demonstration of automotive air-conditioning systems. This poses a significant challenge for students to troubleshoot due to the absence of appropriate training equipment. On the other hand, only one (1) institution utilized a developed car air-conditioning trainer designed for diesel engines, which exhibits a substantial need for improvement to also accommodate gasoline engines. Further improvements for the trainer also include the installation of indicator lights, high- and low-pressure gauges, and an electrical board to facilitate components. Additionally, instructors who are using the existing trainer highlighted the necessity for additional trainers to solve issues of insufficient trainers and outdated or malfunctioning equipment.

It is for these facts that the researcher exerted effort to come up with a study to develop and evaluate a car air-conditioning trainer integrated with charging system as a valuable aid in teaching Automotive Servicing Competencies providing students with hands-on, interactive equipment that will bridge the gap between theory and practice, enabling them to learn the functions of a car air-conditioning system and ensuring them to acquire essential troubleshooting skills and knowledge to satisfy industry standards.

These initiatives aligned with Edgar Dale's Cone of Experience, which states that learners generally retain ninety percent (90%) of knowledge when simulating or modeling a real experience. Furthermore, John Dewey's theory, Pragmatism, emphasizes that

education should not only transmit knowledge but also foster practical skills and encourage critical thinking through active engagement rather than passive reception of information.

The development of a portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system can serve as a valuable educational tool, aiming to enhance practical learning experience, improve educational outcomes, and better prepare students for professions in the automotive industry. This trainer will also enhance the delivery of lessons, providing instructors with a manipulable training device that simulates car AC operations. Integrating this educational tool into institutions like NVSU can further strengthen their commitment to SDG 4, ensuring that both teachers and students have access to quality, skills-based education.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to develop a Car Air Conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system that will serve as one of the teaching aids in imparting technical knowledge to students on the course Bachelor in Technical-Vocational Education major in Automotive.

Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the process in designing and constructing a Car Air Conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system?
2. What is the performance of the trainer based on standard reading using an instrument/tester?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the developed portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system in terms of:
 - a. Design
 - b. Construction
 - c. Functionality
 - d. Safety and
 - e. Durability
4. What is the general level of acceptability of the developed and evaluated portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system, as evaluated by the different groups of respondents?
5. Is there a significant difference in the general level of acceptability of the developed portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system as evaluated by different groups of respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-evaluative developmental research design. The developmental research method was utilized to allow the researcher to combine the

research approach with project development in designing the car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system. Developmental research refers to conditions in which the product-development process is analyzed and explained, and the final product is evaluated (Richey & Klein, 2005). It has made significant contributions to the field's overall progress, frequently providing the foundation for model design and theorizing.

Furthermore, the descriptive-evaluative research design was also used to evaluate the developed Car Air Conditioning Trainer integrated with a charging system. The evaluation focused on key aspects, including its design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability. Data collection instruments included questionnaires distributed to students and experts, comprising instructors and industry technicians.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of the study consisted of students and experts, specifically instructors and technicians, totaling 60 individuals. The study employed a purposive sampling method, wherein respondents were selected based on specific criteria to ensure that their expertise and roles aligned with the objectives of the study.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents

Students		Experts			Total
BTVTED	BSIT	Public Instructors	Private Instructors	Industry Technicians	
6	40	7	2	5	60

The table illustrates the distribution of respondents who participated in answering the survey questionnaires, with a total of sixty (60) individuals. This included six (6) third-year Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (BTVTEd) majors in Automotive Technology students and forty (40) third-year Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology (BSIT) students from Nueva Vizcaya State University (NVSU), Bayombong and Bambang Campuses for the school year 2024–2025. Additionally, nine (9) automotive instructors were included, seven (7) from public and two (2) from private institutions, as well as five (5) industry experts.

Data Gathering Instrument

The study employed an adapted questionnaire from the study of Samonte and Torres (2013), *Development of Car Aircon Trainer*, to evaluate the design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability of the Car Air Conditioning Trainer integrated with a charging system.

The prepared survey questionnaire consisted of two (2) parts: Part I covered the respondents' profile, while Part II presented a set of criteria used to rate the design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability of the trainer.

The weight, range, and descriptive equivalent are indicated below:

Numerical Value	Mean Range	Qualitative Description
5	4.21-5.00	Excellent
4	3.41-4.20	Very Satisfactory
3	2.61-3.40	Satisfactory
2	1.81-2.60	Fair
1	1.00-1.80	Poor

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure was conducted in several phases to address the research objectives. First, the development and construction of the car air conditioning trainer, integrated with a charging system, were documented. This included the design process, material selection, and assembly. Visual aids such as perspective drawings, orthographic sketches, and exploded views were employed to provide a comprehensive illustration of the trainer. A narrative description was also utilized to document the sequential steps involved in developing the trainer.

To evaluate the performance of the trainer, testers were used, and multiple trials were conducted to ensure reliability.

The trainer's design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability were evaluated by various respondents. A formal request for approval to conduct the evaluation was submitted to the University President and the shop managers. Letters of request were also sent to both campuses of NVSU, Bayombong and Bambang, as well as to automotive shops and establishments employing automotive technicians who are considered experts in the automotive industry.

The results were analyzed using statistical tools to identify significant differences in the general acceptability of the trainer based on the responses of the various groups included in the study.

Statistical Tools and Data Analysis Procedure

The data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The following statistical tools were utilized:

The Weighted Mean was used to analyze the respondents' evaluation of the design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability of the developed portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer integrated with a charging system.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine significant differences in the responses of the respondents across the variables of the study. A significance level of 0.05 was used in the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Design Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer Integrated with Charging System

The researcher patterned the construction of the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system from the study of Samonte & Torres (2013). The following were taken into consideration:

The portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system:

1. Should be suited to the curriculum/subjects. It is appropriate for Automotive teachers, students, and industry experts at their level of understanding.
2. In constructing the trainer, locally and commercially available supplies and materials shall be used.
3. It is manually operated, user-friendly, and suitable for the learner for their practical hands-on application.

Figure 1. Portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with charging system exploded view

Table 2. Parts and functions of the portable car air conditioning trainer are integrated with the charging system.

Letter	Parts	Functions
A	Voltmeter	Used to monitor battery voltage, check the charging system's performance, and help diagnose electrical issues. It ensures the battery operates within the proper range (12V–14V) and detects undercharging or overcharging, which could indicate faults in the alternator, regulator, or wiring. "It monitors the current drawn by the air conditioning system and the charging system's output. It helps diagnose issues such as excessive current draw, which may indicate a short circuit, or insufficient charging current, which could point to a failing alternator or faulty wiring."
B	Ammeter	Controls the power supply to the electrical systems and enables charging.
C	Ignition Switch	Displays the battery's charging status.
D	Charge Indicator	Used to measure the pressure of the refrigerant in an air conditioning system
E	Manifold Gauge	"Protects the trainer from dust, scratches, and damage. It also helps prevent accidental contact that may harm students and instructors."
F	Screen Cover	Supplies power to the air conditioning system and electrical components.
G	Battery	Responsible for absorbing heat from the air, causing the refrigerant to evaporate and cool down the air.
H	Evaporator Unit	Generates electricity to charge the battery and power the electrical systems, keeping the battery charged and ensuring the air conditioning system and other components work properly.
I	Alternator	"Drives multiple components in the motor, such as the alternator and air conditioning compressor. "
J	Fan Belt	Pressurizes the refrigerant and circulates it through the air conditioning system. It compresses the low-pressure refrigerant gas, turning it into a high-pressure gas, which is then sent to the condenser for cooling."
K	Compressor	Simulates the vehicle's engine by providing mechanical power to drive various components, such as the compressor and alternator. It converts electrical energy into mechanical energy, allowing the trainer's air
L	Electric Motor	

		conditioning and charging systems to operate."
M	Circuit Breaker	"A safety device that automatically interrupts the flow of electricity if the current exceeds a safe level. It protects the electrical components from damage caused by overcurrent or short circuits, ensuring the system operates safely and preventing potential hazards." "Used to control the power supply to high-power components, such as the compressor or electric motor. When activated, the contactor allows electrical current to flow, enabling the operation of the trainer."
N	Contactor Switch	Ensures that the electrical voltage supplied to the system remains stable and within the required range. It prevents voltage fluctuations that could damage sensitive components like the battery, alternator, and air conditioning system."
O	Voltage Regulator	Houses multiple fuses that protect the electrical components from overloads or short circuits.
P	Fuse Box	Removes moisture and impurities from the refrigerant in the air conditioning system.
Q	Filter Drier	Monitors the refrigerant pressure within the AC system.
R	Pressure Switch	A flexible electrical wire that connects the trainer to a power source.
S	AC Cord	"Helps to improve airflow and cooling efficiency. It assists in maintaining the proper temperature of the condenser and other components by increasing air circulation, preventing overheating."
T	Auxiliary Fan	"Responsible for cooling and converting the high-pressure refrigerant gas from the compressor into a liquid. It releases the heat absorbed by the refrigerant and dissipates it into the surrounding air, allowing the refrigerant to condense and flow back into the evaporator to continue the cooling cycle."
U	Condenser	"Provides structural support for all the components, holding them securely in place."
V	Frame	"A mounted surface that displays key components, such as the air conditioning refrigeration cycle, charging system diagram, and wiring diagrams."
W	Board	"Allows for easy movement and positioning of the trainer that enables the wheels to rotate 360 degrees, making it easy to maneuver,
X	Swivel Lock Caster wheel	

while the lock function ensures the trainer stays securely in place during use, preventing any unwanted movement."

Figure 2. An actual portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system

Construction of Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer Integrated With a Charging System

Table 3. Tools and equipment used in the construction of the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system.

Tools	Functions
Tri-square	Marking and checking 90-degree angles.
Pliers	It is used for holding and gripping.
Vise Grip	To clamp tight and lock, get current measurement; free a stripped bolt, and more.
Pull Push Rule	It is used to measure the length of materials before cutting.
Chipping Hammer	It is used to remove slag from the welded metals.
Machines and Equipment	Functions
Welding Machine	It is an electric-operated machine for welding or joining pieces of metal.
Spray Gun	It is used to spray paint onto a surface.
Grinder	It is used for grinding, cutting, and removing excess materials, sharpening, sanding, and polishing.
Drill	It is used for making round holes or driving fasteners.
Personal Protective Equipment	Functions
Hand Gloves	Protect hands from heat, sparks, and electric shock during welding.
Welding mask	protects the welder's face and eyes from harmful radiation (like UV and infrared), intense light, sparks, and hot metal during welding.
Goggles	It is used to protect the eyes from glaring and sharp materials when welding.

The tools, equipment, and personal protective equipment (PPE) listed in Table 3 summarize the main activities involved in constructing the trainer. These activities include measuring and cutting raw materials, welding components to assemble a portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system, grinding to smooth welded surfaces and edges for safety, and painting the finished product to prevent rusting. PPE such as welding masks, gloves, safety goggles, and protective clothing was used throughout to ensure safety during these processes.

Table 4. List of materials for constructing the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with charging systems

Construction of Main Parts	Measurement	Materials	No. of Days
1. Frame assembly	600 cm 600 cm	Tubular Steel Angle Bar	6

	1 liter	Primer Gray Spray Paint	
2. Painting	2 liter	Lucky Orange Enamel Paint	4
	8 bottles	Paint thinner	
3. Installation of Parts	20 pcs	Aircon Components	12
	40 pc	Bolts and Nuts	
	5 pc		
Total			22

Table 4 presents the construction timeline of the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system. Based on the data, the construction of the frame assembly required six (6) days. The painting process of the frame assembly took an additional four (4) days, resulting in a clean and smooth surface finish. The installation of components took six (12) days to complete. Overall, the entire construction process was completed in twelve (22) days.

It is worth noting that most of the required parts were sourced from the local market, which significantly contributed to the efficiency of the construction process. These findings suggest that the development of a portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system is feasible within a relatively short time frame, provided that the necessary materials and components are readily available.

Table 5. Production cost of constructing a portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system.

Quantity	Unit	Description	Unit Price	Amount
1	pc	AC Cord	250.00	250.00
1	pc	Acrylic glass	1800.00	1800.00
1	pc	Alternator	5500.00	5500.00
1	pc	Ammeter	450.00	450.00
1	pc	Angle Bar 1.5 inches	350.00	350.00
30	Meter	Automotive wire #22	375.00	375.00
5	Meter	Automotive wire #10	35.00	175.00
1	pc	Auxiliary Fan	500.00	500.00
1	pc	Battery	6000.00	6000.00
2	pc	Battery terminal	120.00	240.00
50	pcs	Bolts	400.00	400.00
7	Pc	Circuit Breaker 20A	260.00	260.00
1	Pc	Compact Evaporator	2300.00	2300.00
1	pc	Condenser	1500.00	1500.00
1	pc	Contact Switch	180.00	180.00
1	pc	Compressor	3300.	3300.00
5	pcs	Cutting Disc	25.00	250.00
1	pcs	Cycle and Diagram Layout	500.00	500.00
1	pcs	Digital Voltmeter	150.00	150.00
1	pc	Electric Motor	7500.00	7500.00

1	pc	Electrical Tape	50.00	50.00
2	Liter	Enamel Paint Orange	200.00	400.00
1	Pack	Eye Terminal	160.00	160.00
2	pcs	Fan belt V type	450.00	900.00
1	pc	Filter	170.00	170.00
1	kg	Freon R134a	450.00	450.00
1	Set	Fuse Box	450.00	450.00
1	Set	Gauge Manifold	700.00	700.00
1	Pack	Heat shrink Hose	100.00	100.00
1	spool	Ignition Switch	250.00	250.00
1	pcs	Indicator Light	.00	1000.00
1	pc	Male Plug	35.00	35.00
1	liter	Metal Primer Gray	155.00	155.00
8	Bottle	Paint Thinner	55.00	440.00
5	pcs	Pressure Hose Installation	4,305.00	4,305.00
1	pc	Pressure Switch	450.00	450.00
3	pcs	Sand Paper 800	20.00	60.00
4	pcs	Screen Cover	500.00	2000.00
1	pc	Sticker	2000.00	2000.00
4	pcs	Swivel Lock Caster Wheel	200.00	800.00
3	pcs	Tubular Steel	435.00	1,305.00
1	pc	Voltage Regulator	900.00	900.00
2	kg	Welding Rod	80.00	160.00
			TOTAL	49,465.00

Out of the total cost, ₱42,690.00 or 86.28% was allocated for materials, covering essential components such as the compressor, electric motor, battery, wires, gauge manifold, and structural elements. An amount of ₱3,000.00 or 6.06% was spent on labor, which included the cost of assembling, welding, installing, and finishing the unit. Meanwhile, ₱3,775.00 or 7.63% was used for miscellaneous expenses, which covered transportation, tools, personal protective equipment (PPE), and consumables such as paint and thinner.

This cost-effectiveness aligns with findings from previous studies. For instance, Tagle (2023) emphasized the importance of affordability in the development of educational tools. Similarly, Castillo (2019) highlighted that teachers should utilize instructional technologies that are affordable, ready-to-use, and beneficial for student learning.

Performance Evaluation of Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer Integrated With a Charging System

Table 6. Performance evaluation of air conditioning in terms of cooling effect

Standard Temperature for Car A/C		Temperature Measured for the Car Aircon Trainer		Remarks
Thermostat Setting	Standard Temperature Range (°C)	Thermostat Setting	Measured Temperature (°C)	
1°C	21°C – 27°C	1°C	24°C	Within standard

Table 7. Performance evaluation of air conditioning in terms of high-pressure and low-pressure

Standard Pressure Required for Car A/C				Measured Pressure				Remarks
High Pressure		Low Pressure		High Pressure		Low Pressure		
Not Working	Working	Not Working	Working	Not Working	Working	Not Working	Working	
75 psi	195-250 psi	75 psi	35-50 psi	75 psi	200 psi	75 psi	45 psi	Within standard

Table 8. Performance evaluation of the charging system

Test Parameter	Standard Value (DCv)	Measured Value (DCv)	Remarks
Charging System Voltage Output (Idle)	12.5 – 14.7	12-13.4 Dcv	Pass
Charging System Voltage Output (Load)	12.0 – 14.2	12.5 Dcv	Pass
Charging System Voltage (Max Output)	≤ 15.0	14.7 Dcv	Within

The trainer's performance was evaluated based on cooling effect, pressure levels, and charging system voltage output. The results showed that the trainer met the standard performance criteria, making it a valuable educational tool (see Tables 6-8). This is consistent with the findings of Dinglasan et al. (2008), who also developed an effective auto air conditioning instructional trainer.

Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer in terms of Design and Construction, Functionality, Safety, and Durability Criteria

Tables 9-12 below present a summary of the evaluation of the three respondents on the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system. The evaluation results of the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system.

Table 9. Level of acceptability of the proposed portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system in terms of design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability.

Design Aspect	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The design is suited for self-paced learning.	4.93	0.252	Excellent
2. It is environmentally friendly. (Uses non-ozone depleting gas, no fumes from live engine, no ventilation is necessary.)	4.90	0.354	Excellent
3. The components are comprehensively arranged and easy to manipulate	4.92	0.334	Excellent
4. The trainer feature can simulate real faults.	4.88	0.324	Excellent
5. The trainer represents authentic and actual parts of an automotive air conditioning system integrated with the charging system.	4.93	0.252	Excellent
Average	4.91	0.237	Excellent
Construction Aspect	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The trainer is easy to transfer.	4.90	0.303	Excellent
2. The frame is constructed from high-strength materials to provide a stable foundation for the car air conditioning trainer.	4.90	0.303	Excellent
3. The panel board set-up is easy to understand.	4.93	0.312	Excellent
4. The main components are properly labeled and identified.	4.92	0.334	Excellent
5. The size of the wire and connectors is appropriate for the purpose.	4.95	0.220	Excellent
Average	4.92	0.218	Excellent
Functionality Aspect	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The trainer can demonstrate the cooling effect of a car air conditioner.	4.93	0.252	Excellent
2. The trainer can demonstrate an electrical circuit for a car air conditioner.	4.90	0.303	Excellent

3. It can be utilized for training, like troubleshooting and servicing activities.	4.95	0.220	Excellent
4. The trainer charges the system correctly and maintains proper voltage levels	4.92	0.334	Excellent
5. The trainer is easy to operate/manipulate.	4.90	0.303	Excellent
Average	4.92	0.19	Excellent
Safety Aspect	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The rotating parts of the trainer do not expose students to possible injuries.	4.88	0.324	Excellent
2. Fuse protection is in place in all electrically operated components.	4.92	0.279	Excellent
3. Binding posts and connection leads are properly insulated.	4.88	0.372	Excellent
4. The trainer has protection against incorrect battery connections.	4.88	0.324	Excellent
5. Warning signage or safety precautions are visible in the trainer.	4.93	0.252	Excellent
Average	4.90	0.231	Excellent
Durability Aspect	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
1. The trainer's frame is mechanically stable and built to withstand vibrations.	4.88	0.324	Excellent
2. The trainer's surface is properly coated and resistant to corrosion and rust	4.92	0.334	Excellent
3. The components of the trainer remain securely attached after the lengthy operation.	4.95	0.220	Excellent
4. The trainer stand and frame are made of high-quality and durable materials	4.90	0.303	Excellent
5. The trainer buttons, switches, and controls maintain functionality over time.	4.97	0.181	Excellent
Average	4.92	0.221	Excellent

The table shows the evaluation of the developed portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system across five key aspects: design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability.

In terms of design, the trainer was considered highly effective for self-paced learning, with an average mean score of 4.93, reflecting its suitability for independent study. It was also praised for being environmentally friendly, utilizing non-ozone-depleting gas and eliminating the need for ventilation, receiving a mean score of 4.90. The trainer's components were found to be well-arranged and easy to manipulate, which scored 4.92. Additionally, it was appreciated for its ability to simulate real faults (mean score of 4.88) and accurately represent authentic automotive air conditioning parts integrated with a charging system, with a score of 4.93. These factors contribute to the trainer's exceptional design, making it highly effective for educational purposes, contributing to realistic

learning as stipulated in the findings of Talan (2021), which emphasized the effectiveness of realistic simulations in enhancing learners' technical skills.

The construction of the trainer was equally well-received. It scored an average of 4.92, reflecting its excellent build quality. Respondents highlighted the trainer's easy portability (mean of 4.90) and its strong frame made from high-strength materials, providing a stable foundation (mean of 4.90), an essential feature in vocational learning. The setup of the panel board was clear and easy to understand (mean of 4.93), and the components were properly labeled (mean of 4.92). The trainer also used appropriately sized wires and connectors, scoring 4.95. This aspect ensures that the trainer is practical, user-friendly, and durable for repeated use.

In terms of functionality, the trainer demonstrated exceptional performance with an average of 4.92. It effectively demonstrated the cooling effect of a car air conditioner (mean of 4.93) and its electrical circuits (mean of 4.90). The trainer was also valued for its potential use in various training activities, such as troubleshooting and servicing (mean of 4.95), and its charging system maintained proper voltage levels (mean of 4.92). Additionally, the trainer was deemed easy to operate and manipulate (mean of 4.90), confirming its suitability for hands-on learning experiences.

Regarding safety, the trainer received an average mean score of 4.90, indicating that it meets high safety standards. The rotating parts were designed to prevent exposure to potential injuries (mean of 4.88), and fuse protection was in place for all electrically operated components (mean of 4.92). The binding posts and connection leads were properly insulated (mean of 4.88), and the trainer included protection against incorrect battery connections (mean of 4.88). Additionally, warning signage and safety precautions were visible (mean of 4.93), ensuring that the trainer provides a safe learning environment for students.

In terms of durability, the trainer excelled, with an average of 4.92. The frame was mechanically stable and resistant to vibrations (mean of 4.88), and the surface was properly coated to resist corrosion and rust (mean of 4.92). The components remained securely attached even after prolonged operation (mean of 4.95), and the stand and frame were made of high-quality, durable materials (mean of 4.90). Moreover, the buttons, switches, and controls maintained functionality over time (mean of 4.97), underscoring the trainer's long-lasting performance and reliability.

Overall, the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system was highly regarded across all five aspects. Its design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability were all rated as "Excellent," with means ranging from 4.90 to 4.97. These results demonstrate that the trainer is an effective, safe, durable, and well-constructed educational tool, ideal for teaching and training students on automotive air conditioning systems.

Level of Acceptability of the Proposed Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer as Evaluated by the Different Groups of Respondents

Table 10. General level of acceptability of the proposed portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system, as evaluated by the different groups of respondents.

Criteria	Students		Technicians		Instructors	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Design	4.94	Excellent	4.60	Excellent	5.00	Excellent
Construction	4.93	Excellent	4.73	Excellent	5.00	Excellent
Functionality	4.94	Excellent	4.67	Excellent	5.00	Excellent
Safety	4.93	Excellent	4.67	Excellent	4.98	Excellent
Durability	4.95	Excellent	4.67	Excellent	4.98	Excellent

The table presents the general level of acceptability of the developed and evaluated portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system, as assessed by different groups of respondents, which was overwhelmingly positive.

For the design aspect, students rated the trainer with a mean score of 4.94, technicians gave it a mean of 4.60, and instructors rated it a perfect 5.00. This indicates that the design was well-received by all groups, particularly by instructors who gave it the highest rating.

In terms of construction, the trainer again received excellent ratings, with students rating it 4.93, technicians scoring it 4.73, and instructors giving it another perfect score of 5.00. This shows that the trainer's construction was considered strong, user-friendly, and practical for use by all groups.

The functionality of the trainer was similarly rated highly, with students giving it a mean of 4.94, technicians scoring it 4.67, and instructors once again awarding a perfect score of 5.00. The trainer's ability to perform well in demonstrating the cooling effect, electrical circuits, and its charging system was recognized as excellent by all respondent groups.

Regarding safety, the students rated it 4.93, technicians gave it 4.67, and instructors again rated it very highly with 4.98. This reflects the importance of safety in the trainer's design, ensuring that all users feel comfortable and secure when interacting with the equipment.

Lastly, the durability of the trainer was highly regarded across the board, with students rating it 4.95, technicians scoring it 4.67, and instructors giving it 4.98. This indicates that the trainer's long-term performance and ability to withstand usage over time were highly valued by all groups, especially instructors.

The data shows a high level of satisfaction with the trainer across all aspects, with the majority of ratings falling into the excellent category. The slightly lower evaluations from technicians, notably for durability, indicate areas for targeted improvements to satisfy the higher expectations of technical professionals. This feedback provides essential insights for refining the trainer to ensure it meets the highest standards of quality and performance.

These results are similar to the findings of Samonte & Torres (2013) on the development and assessment of a car air-conditioner trainer found as highly acceptable and valid in terms of design, construction, function, safety, and relevance and received "Excellent" ratings across design, construction, functionality, safety, and durability from students, technicians, and instructors. Likewise, the study of Tagle et al (2023) on the development and assessment of an air-conditioning system trainer emphasized the importance of hands-on experience, reliability, durability, and safety, with consistent results highly accepted by respondents. Both studies underscore the trainer's value in providing practical, real-world experience in a controlled and safe environment.

Overall, the portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system received excellent evaluations across all criteria from students, technicians, and instructors, with mean scores ranging from 4.60 to 5.00. This suggests that the trainer is widely accepted and considered effective, safe, and durable by all respondent groups.

Comparison in the General Level of Acceptability of the Developed Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer Integrated with a Charging System, as Evaluated by Different Groups of Respondents.

Table 11. Evaluation of the differences in the general level of acceptability of the developed portable car air conditioning trainer integrated with a charging system across different groups of respondents.

Criteria	F-value	p-value	Comparison	Decision	Remark
Design	7.419	0.001	p-value < 0.05	reject Ho	The difference is significant.
Construction	3.025	0.056	p-value > 0.05	accept Ho	The difference is not significant.
Functionality	7.238	0.002	p-value < 0.05	reject Ho	The difference is significant.
Safety	3.726	0.030	p-value < 0.05	reject Ho	The difference is significant.
Durability	5.213	0.008	p-value < 0.05	reject Ho	The difference is significant.

Table 12. Post Hoc analysis of data among the three groups of respondents

Criteria	(I) Group	(J) Group	Mean Difference (I-J)	p-value
Design	Students	Technicians	0.3378*	0.002
		Instructors	-0.0622	0.708
	Technicians	Students	-0.3378*	0.002
		Instructors	-0.4000*	0.002
	Instructors	Students	0.0622	0.708
		Technicians	0.4000*	0.002
Functionality	Students	Technicians	0.2711*	0.002
		Instructors	-0.0622	0.605
	Technicians	Students	-0.2711*	0.002
		Instructors	-0.3333*	0.002
	Instructors	Students	0.0622	0.605
		Technicians	0.3333*	0.002
Safety	Students	Technicians	0.2622*	0.023
		Instructors	0.0178	0.974
	Technicians	Students	-.2622*	.023
		Instructors	-.2444	.100
	Instructors	Students	-.0178	.974
		Technicians	.2444	.100
Durability	Students	Technicians	.2800*	.008
		Instructors	-.0311	.911
	Technicians	Students	-.2800*	.008
		Instructors	-.3111*	.016
	Instructors	Students	.0311	.911
		Technicians	.3111*	.016

The table presents the analysis of the general level of acceptability of the developed portable car air conditioning trainer, integrated with a charging system, which reveals significant differences among the groups for certain criteria.

For Design, the F-value is 7.419 with a p-value of 0.001, which is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant difference between the groups. Post hoc analysis reveals that the differences in the design ratings occur between students and technicians, with a mean difference of 0.3378, and between technicians and instructors, with a mean difference of -0.4000. These differences are statistically significant (p-value < 0.05), suggesting that the groups evaluated the design of the trainer differently. These findings align with the study by Begrich et al. (2020), which emphasized how different educational

backgrounds and roles (students, experts, instructors) influence perceptions of instructional quality.

For Construction, the F-value is 3.025 with a p-value of 0.056, which is greater than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference in how the different groups evaluated the construction aspect of the trainer.

In terms of Functionality, the F-value is 7.238 with a p-value of 0.002, which is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant difference between the groups. Post hoc analysis shows that the differences occur between students and technicians, with a mean difference of 0.2711, and between technicians and instructors, with a mean difference of -0.3333. These differences are statistically significant (p-value < 0.05), highlighting that the groups evaluated the functionality of the trainer differently. These differences reflect the varying levels of technical expertise, aligning with the findings of Kline et al. (2021), who noted that hands-on practitioners and learners tend to rate functionality based on immediate usability, whereas instructors often assess based on educational integration.

For Safety, the F-value is 3.726 with a p-value of 0.030, which is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant difference between the groups. The post hoc analysis reveals that the differences occur between students and technicians, with a mean difference of 0.2622, and between technicians and instructors, with a mean difference of -0.2444. However, the difference between students and instructors is not statistically significant (p-value = 0.974). This suggests that while students and technicians differed significantly in their safety evaluations, instructors' evaluations were more aligned with those of the students. This supports the findings of Bernadez et al. (2024) that instructors and students often align in their perception of safety due to shared training environments, while technicians prioritize occupational safety based on field experience.

For Durability, the F-value is 5.213 with a p-value of 0.008, which is less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant difference between the groups. Post hoc analysis shows that the differences occur between students and technicians, with a mean difference of 0.2800, and between technicians and instructors, with a mean difference of -0.3111. These differences are statistically significant (p-value < 0.05), meaning that the groups evaluated the durability of the trainer differently. These findings align with the study of Lebow et al. (2013), which suggested that industry-based practitioners often have more critical evaluations of durability due to exposure to long-term use scenarios.

The difference in the responses of the three groups of respondents, students, instructors, and technicians, revealed differences in perception of the trainer. On the study of Begrich et al. (2020) highlighted differences in first impression of instructional quality between students, educational research experts, and instructors revealing varied reliable ratings based on their backgrounds and experiences, which align with the observed differences in the ratings of the trainer's functionality, safety, and durability by students, instructors, and technicians. The differences in ratings observed in the current study reflect the varied backgrounds and experiences of students, instructors, and technicians. These results are further supported by Lavoie (2011), who emphasized that multi-group

evaluations can reveal critical insights in instructional design through triangulated feedback.

In summary, there are significant differences in the general level of acceptability for the criteria of Design, Functionality, Safety, and Durability among the groups. The significant differences primarily occur between students and technicians, with students generally rating the trainer higher in several aspects. However, for Construction, no significant differences were found between the groups. The post hoc analysis identifies which groups specifically showed significant differences in their evaluations wherein technicians consistently show significant differences in ratings compared to students and instructors across four aspects while students and instructors generally do not show significant differences in their evaluations, providing a deeper understanding of where the discrepancies lie in the assessments of the portable car air conditioning trainer.

Table 13. Comments and Suggestions of the Respondents

Automotive students Comments and Suggestions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Maganda ang prototype <i>madaling mapag aralan</i> and functionality ng aircon ng <i>isang sasakyan</i>.• The product is good.• To be honest <i>wala na po ako maisuggest kase kompleto at maganda naman ang trainer madaling masundan ang proseso</i>.• Improve the power supply into solar panels to reduce energy consumption
Instructors/ Technicians Comments and Suggestions
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Install more durable conduit and a fault finder indicator.• More illuminated wiring diagram.• Use a variable-speed motor to represent variable engine speed.• There should be a variable speed to test the cooling system if there is an effect if it is in lower speed.• Auxiliary fan - to be replaced with a bigger/higher speed.• Just change the position of the auxiliary fan blade.

Table 17 presents a summary of the respondents' comments and suggestions. The notable strengths of the tool will be retained, while the provided recommendations will be considered for further enhancement of the trainer.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the development of the portable car air conditioning trainer demonstrates the feasibility of creating a cost-effective, user-friendly, and curriculum-aligned instructional device for technical-vocational education. Utilizing locally available materials and authentically arranged components, the trainer promotes hands-on, self-paced learning and is practical for integration into educational settings. Its ability to meet standard performance criteria confirms its effectiveness in realistically simulating automotive air conditioning systems, making it a valuable tool for both instruction and diagnostics. The generally high level of acceptability from students, instructors, and technicians reinforces its educational relevance, although slightly more critical feedback from technicians suggests areas for enhancement to better align with industry standards. The strong agreement between students and instructors further emphasizes its appropriateness for pedagogical use. These findings imply that encouraging the development of similar instructional devices can significantly strengthen practical skills training, bridge the gap between theory and real-world application, and contribute to the advancement of technical education programs by providing affordable, functional, and adaptable learning tools.

Recommendations

Given the foregoing findings and conclusions, this study recommends the following:

1. Future versions of the trainer should maintain curriculum-based frameworks and enhance user accessibility features, like modular components or an instructional guide, to support self-paced learning.
2. Implement a routine testing schedule to ensure the trainer consistently meets the standard performance criteria for cooling effect, pressure levels, and charging system voltage output. Use feedback from users to make continuous improvements to the trainer's design and functionality, ensuring it remains up-to-date with industry standards.
3. Enhance the trainer's educational value through working closely with educational institutions by integrating the trainer into automotive air conditioning courses.
4. Address areas where technicians rated the trainer lower, such as construction, functionality, and durability, by incorporating additional technical features or functionalities through gathering insights from industry professionals to meet industry-level standards. Establish a robust feedback mechanism to collect input from students, technicians, and instructors to make data-driven decisions for future improvements.
5. To reconcile the differing perspectives among respondents, it is recommended to pilot test the trainer in actual workshop environments or training centers to collect performance data under real-world conditions. The insights gained can help refine the trainer's design, functionality, safety, and durability aspects that are particularly relevant to fieldwork, enhancing the tool's credibility and acceptability among technicians.

6. Refinement of the trainer based on the technicians' feedback to address specific concerns, particularly in its functionality, safety, and durability, to meet industry-level standards.
7. Extend testing to actual scenarios to validate the trainer's performance under stress to improve its design, functionality, safety, and durability.
8. Integrate the trainer into automotive teaching supported with learning modules, assessment tools, and practical exercises to maximize its instructional impact.
9. Patenting the developed Portable Car Air Conditioning Trainer Integrated with Charging System

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author declares adherence to established ethical standards throughout the conduct of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were also assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents were strictly maintained, and measures were taken to ensure their safety and well-being. No conflicts of interest were present, and all efforts were made to avoid plagiarism. The author ensured an objective and unbiased interpretation of the findings, and the study results were intended solely for academic and research purposes.

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REFERENCES

- Asian Development Bank. (2022, November). /sites/default/files/project-documents/54332/54332-001-pam-en.pdf. Retrieved from www.adb.org: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/project-documents/54332/54332-001-pam-en.pdf>
- Begrich, L. F. (2020). Who sees the most? Differences in students' and educational research experts' first impressions of classroom instruction. *Social Psychology of Education*, 23(3), 673–699. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11218-020-09554-2>
- Bernadez, I. J., Bantilan, A., Quisada, M., Punay, G., Pol, C., Bicog, A., ... Lamanilao, R. (2024). Understanding school safety: Perceptions, realities, and risk factors. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Growth Evaluation*, 5(1), 795–803. <https://doi.org/10.54660/IJMRGE.2024.5.1.795-803>
- Castillo, C. (2019). Innovation delivery of instruction through PROJECT AUTO (Automotive Mock-up Utilization in Training of Grade 11 Students): Input for students' skills

- development in automotive servicing. *Ascendens Asia Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Abstracts*, 3(2E).
<https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/6548>
- Dinglasan, H., Hoplie, F., & Lubigan, E. (2008). Development of an auto air conditioning instructional trainer. Indang, Cavite.
- Kilag, O. T., Mag-aso, J., Poloyapoy, K., Gamboa, A., Mantua, A., & Rivamonte, W. (2023). Technical vocational education in the Philippines for sustainable development. *European Journal of Higher Education and Academic Advancement*, 1(2), 57–70.
<https://doi.org/10.61796/ejheaa.v1i2.102>
- Kline, A. R., Kolegraff, S. A., & Cleary, J. P. (2021). Student perspectives of hands-on experiential learning's impact on skill development using various teaching modalities. In *Proceedings of IConSES 2021 – International Conference on Social and Education Sciences* (pp. 1–10). ISTES Organization.
- Lavoie, D. (2011, December 15). The phased triangulation evaluation model (PTEM). *EDUCAUSE Review*. <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2011/12/the-phased-triangulation-evaluation-model-ptem>
- Lebow, S., Woodward, B., Kirker, G., & Lebow, P. (2013). Long-term durability of pressure-treated wood. *Advances in Civil Engineering Materials*, 2(1), 178–188.
<https://doi.org/10.1520/ACEM20120054>
- Richey, R. C., & Klein, J. D. (2005). Developmental research methods: Creating knowledge from instructional design and development practice. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 16(2), 23–38.
- Samonte, F. A., & Torres, R. G. (2013). Development and assessment of car airconditioner trainer. *Philippine E-Journals*. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=2837>
- Tagle, N. S. (2023). Development and assessment of air-conditioning system trainer. *International Journal of Applied Science and Research*, 5(1), 131–144.
- Talan, T. (2021). The effect of simulation technique on academic achievement: A meta-analysis study. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science (IJTES)*, 5(1), 15–36. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijtes.141>
- Yaodum, T., Mahapoonyanont, N., Nuchanat, J., & Songsung, N. (2023). Experiential learning for higher education students: Why, what, and how? In *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Education and Social Science (ICESS-2023)* (pp. Faculty of Education, Thaksin University).
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